

Lattice and Dynamical Properties of Cadmium Chalcogenides

Buddhi Sagar Pandit^{1*}, Jay Prakash Dubey²

¹PhD scholar, Faculty of science engineering and technology, DR K.N Modi University, India

²Faculty of science engineering and technology, DR K.N Modi University, India

*Email: buddhipandit43@gmail.com

*ORCID: 0009-0001-4281-3873

Abstract

II–VI semiconductors are significant materials for technology because of their direct and relatively broad gap. Interest in these compounds' physical characteristics has increased because the blue-green laser diode based on them was recently successfully fabricated. The elastic, electrical, and lattice dynamical characteristics of chalcogenides (CdS, CdSe, and CdTe) have been studied by ab initio calculations based on norm-conserving pseudo potentials and density functional theory.

The computed band structures, phonon dispersions, lattice parameters, and elastic constants accord well with existing theoretical and experimental findings. Additionally, we discussed how band gaps and elastic constants rely on pressure. The specific objectives of this study are: to assess CdS, CdSe, and CdTe's mechanical stability and elastic constants for device endurance and, to examine electrical characteristics related to light absorption and carrier transport, such as band gap, effective mass, and conductivity.

The current ground state computations are based on the local density approximation (LDA) utilizing the Coperley–Alder (CA) and the first-principles pseudopotential approach inside the density functional formalism. Our main findings concern the lattice dynamical and elastic characteristics of cadmium chalcogenides in zinc blende structures.

Although the bulk moduli are overestimated by 10–15%, we find that the lattice parameters are in great agreement with the measurements. The differences in the bulk moduli might be caused by Siesta or LDA's intrinsic limitations. We think that further theoretical and experimental research is necessary for a thorough explanation of these chemicals in the ZB phase.

Keywords: *elastic constants, lattice dynamics, band structure, properties of cadmium chalcogenides*